

A Model to Predict the Effect of Health Crisis on the Sectors of the Egyptian Stock Market

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Abstract— Stock market forecasting is one of the most common applications for machine learning models, but it is challenging due to the market's volatile nature and non-linear behaviour. It is also affected by factors like the political situation, the global economy, and unexpected health crises like COVID-19. Nowadays, the fintech domain utilizing deep learning models has garnered significant attention from both investors and researchers. Hence, the aim behind this work is to develop a forecasting model for predicting the value of emerging indices in the Egyptian stock market sectors—namely the healthcare, energy, and education sectors, using the LSTM model. Additionally, to enhance the prediction accuracy for the short-term market behaviour across different EGX sectors. Furthermore, this research includes a recommendation feature designed to suggest which sector of the three sectors input to the model may offer the best investment opportunities for the following day to maximize potential profit. To apply our work, daily time series data from three historical sectors of the EGX, along with daily time series data related to COVID-19 in Egypt, were used. For optimal accuracy, two distinct approaches are conducted and evaluated: the univariate LSTM model and the multi-variate LSTM model. After that, the proposed work led to an improvement in the model's performance through a hyperparameter optimization technique that reduced the value of root mean square error (RMSE); thus, the results referred to the application of the multivariate LSTM approach that combines the most correlated data from the sectoral index with the COVID-19 reports related to Egypt, which is the best experiment for determining the following day value of the sectoral index and outperforms well during the market. The model will report the percentage change in value and recommend sectors expected to be profitable the following day which may be valuable when applying it in different health crisis such as the current monkeyPox crisis.

Keywords— Stock Marketing, Covid-19, LSTM, Predictive Model, Uni-Variate, Multi-Variate

I. INTRODUCTION

The stock market is known for its instability and unpredictability. The main objective of stock market stakeholders is to maximize profits and minimize risks through comprehensive market evaluation making it challenging for researchers to predict future stock values. However, the major challenge for researchers is to predict future stock market values with high accuracy and low errors. This will be done by consolidating diverse information and constructing a dependable model for precise prediction. Researchers have been using time-series data to make these predictions, but many parameters impact market changes like Political situations, the global economy, and unexpected health crises. Many health crises in the 20th century affected the stock markets, such as the Spanish flu epidemic, the Asian influenza virus, and the Hong Kong flu. During the 21st century, the world witnessed, four health crises that caused complete paralysis of trade and travel around the world and also affected the economic sector such as set of respiratory acute syndrome (STHERS, Respiratory Acute Severe Middle East Syndrome (2002), Avian influenza H1N1 2009, Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Baldwin and Di Mauro (2013 Fisheye and Ebola, 2012 Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) Corona pandemic. Despite all these health crises mentioned above, but coronavirus pandemic had the most harmful effect on financial markets [1]. The pandemic had a fatal effect on different stock market indices [2] At the beginning of the pandemic, EGX 30 fell from 14000 points to 9000 points, with fluctuations in index value in 2020 [1], as shown in Figure 1. [3].

Fig. 1 EGX Sector

Indices [3]

In addition, all sectoral indices of the Egyptian stock exchange also affected negatively as shown in Figure 2 [4].

Fig. 1 Covid-19 effect on EGX sectors [1]

On the 2nd of January 2020, EGX Sectoral Indices was launched by the Egyptian Exchange. It is considered part of the reclassification of EGX equity market sectors according to a new comprehensive framework aiming to develop and raise the efficiency of the Egyptian capital market [1]. The launched sectoral indices are very important because they give the ability to investors to track the performance of the constituents in each sectoral index [5]. Over the years, there have been a lot of scientific trials to predict stock market indices to make more profit and less loss. They used several statistical analyses, machine learning, and deep learning models to predict different stock market indices. Traditionally, researchers proposed two main approaches to forecasting the future stock price. The first one is technical analysis which is based on historical data. Charts are used in this approach to spot trends and patterns in prices. There are three types of trends (uptrend, downtrend, sideways). The second type of analysis is qualitative, which is performed based on external factors like company profile, market situation, political and economic factors, and textual information in the form of financial news articles, social media, and even blogs by economic analysts [2]. Nowadays, Because of the remarkable progress that has been made in the domain of deep learning and machine learning. It is noticeable that Recurrent Neural networks (RNN) via extensions like LSTM have recorded high performance and more accuracy when they were applied to similar challenges [3]. On the other hand, and through this research; there are a set of challenges that appear in the form of events of Covid and the novelty of the sectoral indices. To address this difficulty, we compared between multivariate and univariate time series. Multivariate time series are more meaningful than the latter one because they have more features than univariate time series. Hence, it's predictable and logical that multivariate time series would make more accurate predictions. The LSTM model has been used to deliver our proposed solution for the addressed problem. It is confirmed that deep learning algorithms can find existing patterns in the data and exploit them by using a soft learning process. Unlike other statistical and machine learning algorithms, not only deep learning can identify short-term as well as long-term dependencies in the data but also they can give good predictions by finding these hidden relationships. [4]. The rest of the paper is structured into the following sections, where the related works are demonstrated through Section II, after which the proposed work is discussed in Section III, the methodology is explained in Section IV, and finally, the results are shown in Section IIV.

II. RELATED WORKS

In the last decades, researchers have focused on predicting the behavior of the stock market. In this study the data used was a daily time series of the NIFTY50 index, authors implemented the ARIMA model on this data set to forecast future values of the stock by employing different variants of the ARIMA model, and they achieved potential improvement in ARIMA Performance. Similarly, in this study, authors used historical data from Netflix for five years and customized two ARIMA models to achieve the best accuracy [6]. But the ARIMA model is still a univariate model the input to the traditional model is one variable (historical data of the desired predicted feature) and stock markets are affected by many factors moreover it doesn't work well with non-linear data despite stock market historical data being non-linear data consequently, there was a need to model that deal with non-linear data furthermore multivariate model to include factors that affect the stock market. With the emergence of deep learning which deals with non-linear data researchers tend to compare traditional models and deep learning models but they found that deep learning models beat the traditional models and record higher accuracy than traditional models like ARIMA in solving classification problems [7]. Moreover, in regression problems, LSTM also outperforms traditional models [8]. Recently, researchers have been focusing on enhancing the accuracy of stock market forecasting by leveraging the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) metric. One approach to achieve this is by adding additional data in addition to the historical stock market analysis and then feeding these features to the multivariate model. By incorporating technical indicators, which are mathematical calculations based on historical price and volume data, researchers aim to capture more nuanced patterns and trends in the stock market. These indicators can provide insights into market sentiment, momentum, volatility, and other relevant factors that can affect stock price movements. In particular, researchers have been exploring the inclusion of technical indicators in their multivariate models. In this study [9] authors used univariate and multivariate LSTM models predicting the short-term stock prices of two Indian companies, experimental results indicated that incorporating technical indicators is beneficial in predicting future price behaviors with a high accuracy level. Furthermore, the consideration of influential factors, such as sentiment analysis which reflect public opinions, is gaining prominence. Events like political and economic opinions can have a significant impact on the stock market, leading to increased volatility and uncertainty. In this research [10], authors applied binary classification using six ML models to

predict the stock exchange and predict which is a better decision to buy or sell, they used three sources of data, historical data of Microsoft company and stock tweets as well as SM data from Twitter. Findings of their experimental result suggest that by leveraging VADER for sentiment analysis and SVM for classification, authors were able to obtain promising results. Although, combining influential factors, technical indicators, and macroeconomic data along with fundamental data can be beneficial but well well-balanced features need to be fed to the suitable, simple, and interpretable model to achieve the general objective of enhancing accuracy so the need for feature selection has appeared. In the study [11], authors incorporated three types of data fundamental, microeconomic, and technical indicators then feature selection was applied by correlation matrix to extract the most correlated features after that Multilayer and single-layer LSTM model was implemented to predict the S&P500 index's closing price. the result showed that LSTM single layer outperforms better than multilayer LSTM. By including these influential factors in the analysis, researchers can better understand and predict the market behavior during such events moreover feature selection increases the performance of the prediction but there is still the problem of forecasting the stock market during the crisis as the stock market has sudden fluctuations and suffers from instability as mentioned in this research [12], authors applied SVM, lasso, Ridge, Bayesian Ridge, and linear regression during Pre-Covid, Early-Covid, and Mid-Covid while SVM excelled during Mid-Covid period, its effectiveness decreased during the initial phase of the pandemic when the market is volatile and have sudden drop and frequent stop. Consequently, in this study, we aim to develop an LSTM model to deal with univariate and multivariate small-sized datasets moreover to extract an optimal set of attributes to predict next day value of any Egyptian sectoral index during any health crisis when the market is unstable and the index has more fluctuation. Then we compare between univariate and multivariate LSTM. In addition to that, Time series data is data that is taken in constant order of time. The most familiar time series example is stock market data. Nowadays, forecasting the stock market is a challenging problem in the economic field because of it is volatility, nonlinearity moreover its dependability on many factors. Over the years, researchers have attempted to forecast the stock market with a high level of accuracy; they used classical time series models which are based on temporal variation inside a time series and work well with univariate time series but don't work well with multivariate time series such as moving average and auto regression to ARIMA [13]. In [14] authors applied (ARIMA) model to the Amman stock market (ASE) for the period from 1993 to 2017 and they have mentioned improving the short-term prediction of the ASE They reached that the ARIMA model of 1.4 RMSE is the best model fitted after their experiments but also they found that in some cases ARIMA model cannot be fitted. Then, the researcher observed that many factors affect negatively or positively the accuracy of forecasting the stock market, so it's necessary to forecast the stock market using models that can deal with multivariate time series data and can be used to extract seasonality and correlation and focus on cause and effect. These models are called supervised learning for example linear regression, random forest, and XGBoost. After that, the appearance of deep learning models which are more complex and produce better results compared to other types —for example, LSTM, Prophet, and deepAR [15] [16]. Researchers tend to apply these models to forecast multivariate time series stock market data to achieve better accuracy than when they applied the previous models. In [15] Authors implement a stacked LSTM model using data from Infosys Limited of Bombay Stock Exchange, India (BSE30), and the result of the model is evaluated using RMSE and MAPE and compared to the performance of Moving Average and XGBoost. They found that LSTM has the best result in evaluation with RMSE 7.8. In [12] researcher applied machine learning algorithms using data from SENSEX, which is the index for stocks in BSE for 17 years to predict the stock market and compare the pre-Covid, early-Covid, and mid-Covid periods. They observed that SVM does not perform adequately when the data are volatile, and the market is unstable. In [16], the authors analyzed data from the Egyptian economy, along with several economic indicators including the quarter inflation rate, GDP, and unemployment, spanning a period of 30 years. They aimed to compare different types of LSTM models for forecasting purposes. The results of their analysis revealed that the convlstm and bidirectional LSTM models outperformed the other two types of models. These findings suggest that these two models are more effective for accurate forecasting in this context. In [17] authors had two objectives: the first one was to study the Herding Behavior in the sectors of the Egyptian Stock Exchange, and the second one was to demonstrate the parameters that impact the Herding Behavior based on the parameters identification. They applied multiple regression techniques to end with coronavirus hurting the following sectors Basic resources, banks, Travel, Health & Care, Pharmaceuticals, and Food, Beverages, and Tobacco. In [18], authors applied three LSTM models (a baseline LSTM model (LSTM), an LSTM model with sentiment indexes (LSTMSA), and an LSTM model with sentiment indexes and the attention mechanism (LSTMSAA). They focus on the comments' bullish and bearish nature, which significantly increased accuracy. They found that LSTMSAA recorded better accuracy than others, as shown in Table 1. One of the most suitable models used in deep learning is the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Model [20]. LSTMs are efficient models especially when using financial datasets [21]They can retain long-term dependencies. This means that they can effectively capture patterns and dependencies in the data that may not be apparent with traditional machine learning algorithms [22]. Additionally, they can handle small datasets by handling overfitting cases. This occurs when a model seems too close to the training data, resulting in poor performance on new data. LSTMs can generalize well on small datasets, which is essential when the dataset is limited in size. Hence those models shared a set of factors to be considered by applying any one of them in the proposed work as concluded in Table 2.

TABLE I
TIME SERIES PREDICTION FOR THE STOCK MARKET

Ref	Year of publication	Dataset	Period	Models	Evaluation	Classification or regression
[15]	2021	historical Dataset of Infosys Limited of Bombay Stock Exchange, India (BSE30)	1year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> LSTM with hyperparameter XGBoost MA 	RMSE for LSTM 7.834 RMSE for MA 10.094 RMSE with XGBoost 8.807	Regression
[12]	2022	SENSEX, which is the index for stocks in BSE.	17 years of data from 2004 to 2020	SVM, regression	Regression is more accurate than SVM	Classification
[16]	2022	data for the Egyptian economy in addition to information on various economic indicators such as the quarter inflation rate, GDP (Gross Domestic Product), and unemployment.	(30 years)	Four types of lstm Stacked -lstm bidirectional-lstm Conv-LSTM CNN-LSTM	Bidirectional and conv-lstm outperform well	Regression
[17]	2020	Sectors of the Egyptian stock market and covid 19 cases and deaths	About 4 months	Multiple regression	-	Regression
[18]	2021	the daily stock closing price of AAPL using the Yahoo Finance API also collected tweets from two separate sources during this time: 289,308 tweets from Stock twits and 437,858 tweets from Twitter	From January 1, 2020, until December 30, 2020.	LSTM	MAPE 2.1 RMSE was about 3.3 for LSTMSAA	Regression
[19]	2019	Historical Data from Nasdaq	From 2009 to2019	Stacked LSTM	RMSE=.04	Regression

TABLE 2
FACTORS FOR SELECTING MODELS [23]

	Linear Regression	Logistics Regression	SVM	CART	Gradient Boosting	Random Forest	ANN	KNN	LDA	LSTM
Simplicity	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NO	NO	NO	Yes	Yes	NO
Training Time	Yes	Yes	NO	Yes	NO	NO	NO	Yes	Yes	NO
Handle Non-Linearity	NO	NO	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Robust to overfitting	NO	NO	Yes	NO	NO	Yes	NO	Yes	NO	NO
Large Dataset	NO	NO	NO	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NOx'	Yes	Yes
Many Features	NO	NO	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NO	Yes	Yes
Model Interpretation	Yes	Yes	NO	Yes	Yes	Yes	NO	Yes	Yes	Yes
Feature Scaling	NO	NO	Yes	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	Yes

The first factor is Simplicity: This means that simpler models typically require less computational power and time to reconstruct, making them more scalable. Additionally, simpler models are usually easier to interpret and understand, which can be advantageous for further analysis and decision-making. However, a high degree of simplicity may also result in a loss of accuracy or predictive power in the model, as it may not capture the complex relationships and interactions present in the data. Therefore LSTM is not a simple model compared to other models because more computationally expensive more memory and time to train is required and it additionally runs due to their additional parameters and operations. But, finding the right balance between simplicity and accuracy is crucial in model development [25] [26].

The second factor is the training of LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) which depends on a lot of parameters, including the size of the dataset, the complexity of the LSTM architecture, the computational resources available, and the optimization algorithms used. In general, training an LSTM model can take a considerable amount of time due to the sequential nature of its

computation and the need to update the weights at each time step. The training time increases with the number of layers in the LSTM architecture and the size of the hidden state. Additionally, larger datasets require more training time as the model needs to process and learn from more samples. However, it is worth noting that the availability of parallel processing frameworks, such as GPUs (Graphics Processing Units), can significantly reduce the training time. Furthermore, optimization algorithms like stochastic gradient descent (SGD), Adam can affect the training time. These algorithms update the weights of the LSTM during training and can have different convergence rates. Through our research, our dataset is small so this factor is not effective in selecting the best suitable model [27].

The third factor is Handling nonlinearity in the data which means The ability of the model to handle the non-linear relationship between the variables. LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) can handle non-linearity in data. LSTM is considered a type of recurrent neural network (RNN) architecture that is well-suited for capturing sequential information and dependencies in the data. Unlike traditional RNNs, LSTM incorporates memory cells and gates that allow it to selectively remember or forget information from previous time steps. This capability enables LSTM to effectively capture long-term dependencies in the data, making it particularly suitable for modeling non-linear relationships and handling sequences with long time lags. This makes LSTM a powerful tool for modeling non-linear relationships in time series, natural language processing, speech recognition, and other sequential data tasks. [28].

The Fourth factor is the ability of the model to handle overfitting, overfitting should be taken into account when forecasting and analyzing financial time series problems as data are not sufficient and the dataset size is small. [29].

The fifth factor is the consideration of the dataset size which is a very important part of training deep learning models (LSTM). it is proportional to the model performance. LSTM like any other deep learning model able to handle large datasets. using a large dataset can prevent the model from overfitting and provide high accuracy and performance. Financial time series data are often small-sized datasets. Therefore, some issues must be taken into account when using small-sized datasets to train LSTM like generalization and overfitting [30].

The sixth factor is the number of features which refers to the model's ability to handle the feature space's high dimensionality. Especially in LSTM, there are two ways to implement it. first one is univariate and the second is multivariate [31].

The seventh factor is a model interpretability which is crucial in choosing the suitable model. it allows us to take concrete actions to solve the underlying problem [32].

The last factor is Feature scaling where the model requires scaled or customarily distributed variables. When using unscaled data with a range of values (10-1000) to fit the model. large inputs may cause the learning and convergence of your model to be slower and in some cases cause performance issues when learning the model. LSTM requires feature scaling [33]. In summary, LSTM models provide multi-variate input and output, and robustness to overfitting but can be solved by regularization and optimization modeling the more complex relationships in the data, handling financial time series data with its properties of non-linearity and its size.

III. PROPOSED WORK

A. Dataset Representation

Datasets are gathered from two sources covering the period from February 2020 to August 2022. The first source is the Egyptian Stock Market (EGX) website and the second source is (the WHO)website. From the first source, the data was extracted from the daily report of EGX sector indices and combined with the daily report of Coronavirus from the second source. The data from the two sources was merged by date. The size of the sample is around 1000 records with 8 features (value, High, Low, New cases, New deaths, Cumulative cases, Cumulative deaths) as referred to in descriptive statistics of data as shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF DATASET

	value	High	low	New cases	Cumulative cases	New deaths	Cumulative deaths
Count	1005.000000	1005.000000	1005.000000	1005.000000	1005.000000	1005.000000	1005.000000
Mean	729.641194	734.623393	725.259801	512.841791	266563.428856	24.674627	13979.870647
Std	104.371911	105.576856	104.053717	579.292932	180497.195498	23.189472	8831.220116
Min	530.970000	537.100000	525.160000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
25%	652.820000	658.330000	646.550000	14.000000	104156.000000	1.000000	6017.000000
50%	711.150000	715.300000	708.120000	343.000000	275010.000000	18.000000	15723.000000
75%	814.620000	821.490000	810.250000	866.000000	473449.000000	43.000000	23857.000000

Max	994.840000	998.370000	992.310000	5516.000000	515406.000000	97.000000	24798.000000
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B. Model Preparation

The different aspects of the proposed model include data collection, data preprocessing, model construction, hyperparameter tuning prediction, and evaluation. as shown in Figure 3. Firstly, the time series dataset is collected and then it is passed through a preprocessing module that includes normalization and preparing input-output to the model. Moreover, the LSTM model is trained using various inputs to forecast the next-day value of the index during a time of crisis. Furthermore, model evaluation was done and parameter tuning using random search was used to enhance our model then evaluation is done. comparative study between the different experiments according to various inputs to the model was done. the lower RMSE and MAPE reached indicate that the suitable input to the model. After that, the model was applied to different sectors such as (the energy sector and education sector in addition to the healthcare sector). the results and percentage of change are stored and then used to feed a recommender system to predict which sector would be the optimal choice for investment. recommendation would be based on the greatest positive percentage of change.

Fig 3: Proposed Architecture

C. Dataset Pre-processing

In this study, sectoral indices for the Healthcare, Energy, and Education sectors of the Egyptian Stock market were collected from the EGX website [34]. Additionally, other influential factors during the time of crisis such as daily COVID-19 reports from the WHO website [35], were used to predict market fluctuations for the following day. A complete dataset was collected starting from February 2020 to 1 November 2022 as shown in Table 4. This time frame selected incorporates the sectoral index since its inception in February 2020 and the daily report of COVID-19 in Egypt country. This ensures that the model construction, which includes both the daily report of the sectoral index and the daily report of COVID-19; accurately reflects the overall market scenario at the time of crisis and the effect of the crisis on the stock market as shown in Figure 6. This approach aims to improve the accuracy of the market prediction. Data is divided into input and output to learn the model what its input and which attribute is the output as the index value for the next day in all experiments:

- Input in univariate is the index value of the previous 50 days, and the output is the next day of the index value
- Input to the second experiment is stock data attributes only
- Input to the third experiment is all features in the two merged datasets
- Input to the fourth experiment is the most correlated feature in the merged dataset as shown from the heat map as shown in Figure 4.

Fig 4: Dataset Correlated Features

TABLE 4
SAMPLE FROM DATASET IN TABULAR FORM

Date	value	High	low	New cases	Cumulative cases	New deaths	Cumulative deaths
2020-02-01	987.13	992.21	987.13	0	0	0	0
2020-02-02	991.12	993.31	987.13	0	0	0	0
2020-02-03	986.44	991.12	986.44	0	0	0	0
2020-02-04	994.84	998.37	986.44	0	0	0	0
2020-02-05	993.40	996.66	992.31	0	0	0	0

D. Model construction and training

Through this phase, the LSTM model is constructed with memory between batches using two LSTM layers with 100 units and two dense layers; the First LSTM layer is adjusted to return sequence but the second isn't adjusted to anything. The impact of setting return sequences to true is that it allows the subsequent layers to receive the sequence output, enabling the model to learn and capture temporal dependencies across the time series data. In other words, the intermediate outputs from the first LSTM layer act as input for the second LSTM layer, which further processes the sequence. In terms of improving mean squared error (MSE), having return sequences is True allows the model to capture more information about the temporal behavior of the time series, which can lead to better predictions. By retaining the entire sequence of output, the model can better identify any patterns and dependencies within the data despite of small size of the data. [36] [19]. The model is trained across 70 epochs and 16 batch sizes using the Adam optimizer and MSE loss function.

E. Hyperparameter tuning

Hyperparameter tuning is a crucial step in the process of building a machine-learning model. The goal of hyperparameter tuning is to find the best set of hyperparameters that will optimize the model's performance and minimize the loss function. After evaluating our models, the best experiment which means the lowest RMSE was taken and hyperparameter optimization was done on it to enhance the accuracy of the prediction. There are several methods to perform hyperparameter tuning, one of which is a random search algorithm. Random search algorithms are used in hyperparameter tuning because they randomly search the space of hyperparameters instead of exhaustively searching the space. This is beneficial because the search space of hyperparameters is

typically very large, and an exhaustive search is computationally expensive and time-consuming. A random search algorithm saves time and computational resources because it only explores a subset of the search space. Hyperparameters for the model. Using a random search algorithm can be an efficient method to find the optimal hyperparameters in less time and validate the model quickly. [37]. The aim of using a random search algorithm for hyperparameter optimization in this research is to construct different models and search the space for the best hyperparameter based on the mean squared error objective. Especially it is used to search for the best number of units in each layer to enhance MSE. We define the space to range from 32 to 128. The tuner will perform a maximum of 10 trials, each trial executing the training procedures 3 times.

IV. RESULTS AND EVALUATION

In this research, the predictive model is used to forecast continuous variables as the mentioned objective is to predict the next-day value of the index; that may refer to a regression problem. In regression problems; to measure the accuracy of the model after training forecast error must be taken into account which is defined as the discrepancy between the actual value and the forecasted value. This difference can be measured using various indicators, including mean absolute error (MAE), mean square error (MSE), and root mean square error (RMSE) that measure accuracy between continuous variables. Statistically, RMSE is a quadratic scoring rule which measures the average magnitude of the error but MAE measures the average magnitude of the errors in a set of forecasts as shown in Equation 1, without considering their direction. MAE and RMSE are negatively-oriented scores which means lower values are better. A smaller RMSE indicates that the model's predictions are closer to the actual values, suggesting a higher level of accuracy in forecasting stock prices.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}, \quad (1)$$

Analysis of results after the training phase

After performing the proposed experiments, the evaluation of executing the different cases indicated that the performance of the multi-variant model using hyper-parameters optimization is the best model for predicting the concurrent value of the stock market according to the effect of COVID-19 especially in the sector EGX30 in the Egyptian stock market. By analyzing the experiment's result and curves, both curves decreased rapidly after 10-15 epochs indicating that the model effectively learns and refines its parameter and improves its prediction although around epoch 10 the training curves are above $6e-4$ following this, both training loss and validation loss are converged closely after ten iterations with errors decreasing and became lower over time then stabilized. While training curve was stabilized at $2e-4$ and the validation loss stabilized but at slightly higher. In summary, the model is well fitted to the data without main problems but there is minimal fluctuation in the validation loss curve which indicates that the model is performing well with variations to unseen data as shown in Figure 5.

Fig 5: Uni-Variate Model Evaluation Chart

On the other hand, At early epochs, there are a sharp decline in the two curves then curves converged to each other at around epoch 25 and begin to stabilize at epoch 40 to reach $1e-4$ for the training curve and validation loss around $2e-4$ to $3e-4$, but the gap between two curves indicate some level of overfitting as shown in Figure 6.

Fig 6: multi-Variate Model Evaluation Chart (stock only)

In addition, in the third experiment, utilizing all features from both datasets, in the initial epochs there are significant fluctuations in both curves particularly in training curve indicating that the model attempt to learn the patterns in the dataset but effective learning hadn't yet occurred then curves begin to converge at about 25 epochs and losses became around 4e-4 but validation loss is much lower than training loss and the validation loss stabilizes at 45 epochs and doesn't decrease further which indicating that under fitting problem is occurred as shown in Figure 7.

Fig 7: Multi-variate Model Evaluation Chart all data of stock and Covid

On the other hand, when applying the multivariate model most correlated features as input, the model rapidly adjust its weights as both the training and validation curves decrease sharply at 0-10 epochs and at 10 epochs training curve is less than 6e-4, after initial sharp decrease the curves begin to converge and stabilizing over time after around epoch 15 at 2e-4 with the loss values flattening out, the final loss values showing that the model learned effectively and performing well with minimal errors there are no signs for overfitting or under fitting .overall performance is that the model is well fitted generalized well to unseen data with minimal errors as shown in Figure 8.

Fig 8: multi-Variate Model Evaluation Chart (most correlated)

Hence, the Fourth experiment is indicated that the well-fitted model to be applied when predicting the next-day stock market index's value according to the summarized table in Table 5.

TABLE 5
COMPARISON BETWEEN EACH PROPOSED RUNNING EXPERIMENT

At early epochs	Convergence and stabilization (loss values)	Gap between curves	fluctuations	Overall performance	Figure no	experiment
10-15 epochs Sharp initial decline	At 10 epochs training curve is above $6e-4$ Stabilized at 25 epochs around $2e-4$	Close to each other	Minor	Learned training data well And generalized reasonably well to unseen data	5	Univariate
Sharp decrease but the validation curve is significantly far from the training curve	Converged at about 25 epochs reach low loss particularly training curve about $1e-4$ But there is a large gap between training and validation loss	Significantly far from each other	Minor	Show signs of overfitting Not generalized well and struggle with unseen data But it shows a lower overall loss	6	Stock data only without covid
significant fluctuations	Is about epoch 25 loss of training is about $6e-4$ Stabilized at 45 epochs but training loss is lower than validation loss	Closed but Training lower than validation	Major	Underfitting concern	7	utilizing all features from both datasets
Initial sharp decrease 0-10 epochs	At epoch 10 training curve less than $6e-4$ stabilized at 15 epochs around $2e-4$	Close to each other	Minor and flattening out after stabilization	Well-fitted and rapidly adjusted Generalized well-to-unseen data with minimal errors	8	Most correlated

Analysis of results after the test phase

Through this section, the results of the performed experiments are conducted. Where measuring the difference between the testing and results data in a ratio of 80:20. In the Uni-Variate experiment, the prediction has lower accuracy against testing data than the accuracy conducted from the experiments of multi-variate using features of stock and covid-19 data, features of stock data only, and finally the multi-variate experiment with most correlated features using hyper parameters optimization. The experiments indicated that the accuracy of prediction against the testing data in the most correlated experiment is the best one of all of them that is because of the high level of convergence between testing and prediction curves, as shown in Figures 9, 10, 11, and 12.

Fig 9: Testing result Vs. Prediction Results in (Uni-Variate Model Experiment)

Fig 10: Testing result Vs. Prediction Results in (Multi-variate Model with features of Stock data only Experiment)

Fig 11: Testing result Vs. Prediction Results in (Multi-variate Model with features of Stock and Covid-19 Experiment)

Fig12: Testing result Vs. Prediction Results in (Multi-variate Model - Most Correlated Experiment)

On the other hand, a larger RMSE suggests that the model's predictions deviate more from the actual values, indicating a lower accuracy in forecasting. Therefore, when comparing different models or forecasting methods, the one with the smaller RMSE is considered to be the better predictor of stock values as shown in Table 6 and Figure 13.

TABLE 6
Value of RMSE for each used model

Experiment	MAPE %	RMSE Value
Univariate LSTM	0.76	6.394200950464784
Multi-variate using stock fields only	0.75	5.275582799547984
Multi-variate using COVID data	0.52	3.549500400791034
Multi-variate with the most correlated feature	0.46	2.55001661
Multi-variate using most correlated with hyper-parameter	0.15	0.0379291771506715

Fig 13: Comparison of RMSE Values Chart for all used models

In addition to that, the second phase after predicting the value of index all over the different inspected sectors such as, healthcare, energy, and education sectors. The proposed model recommend that the most suitable sector to invest through the crisis is the educational sector according to its highest value of percentage of change as shown in Figure 14.while the RMSE of each sector is shown in Table 7.

Predicted next day's percentage change for Education: 0.40%
 Predicted next day's percentage change for Energy: 3.04%
 Predicted next day's percentage change for Healthcare: -0.43%
 The best sector to invest in during the coronavirus pandemic is: Energy

Fig 14: the recommended sector after applying the proposed recommender system

TABLE 7
Value of RMSE for each Sector

Sector	Prediction for next day	Percentage of change%	RMSE
healthcare	981.86	-0.43	0.037929
Energy	581.8400	+3.04	0.013785

Education	1714.3100	+0.4	817.0020
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V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

In this research, a proposed short-term predictive model is achieved using univariate and multivariate LSTM to forecast the value of emerging indices in the Egyptian stock market across healthcare, energy, and education sectors. During health crises and fluctuation (COVID-19 as a case study) and to show how the input to the model affects the accuracy of the model and the prediction. Daily reports of the Egyptian stock market sectorial index and Daily COVID-19 reports in Egypt were collected and used to train the LSTM model. The results showed that the proposed strategy outperformed traditional statistical methods moreover overcame the difficulty of market fluctuation during the crisis and a small dataset. By leveraging hyperparameter optimization, the model's performance was significantly enhanced, as indicated by the reduced RMSE. The proposed model not only forecasts sectorial index values but also provides a recommendation system for identifying the most potentially profitable sector on the following day, thus offering a valuable tool for investors navigating volatile market conditions. On the other hand, the RMSE value of the proposed model is 0.03 so the model can help traders and investors make more profit and avoid loss during the period of crisis. Also, it's planned for future works to improve our predictive model by using sentiment analysis techniques along with the Deep learning model.

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